

GEOMETRICAL CONSEQUENCES OF FATIGUE CRACK DEFLECTION
IN COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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SUMMARY

Recent models which estimate apparent changes in propagation rates arising from known variations in the path of a fatigue crack are reviewed. The *consequences* of periodic tilts in crack profiles are examined as a function of angle of deflection, length of deflection and the amount of net lateral displacement (mismatch) between the mating crack faces. The usefulness of such calculations are discussed in light of the quantitative understanding of the *trends* in *local* mixed-mode fracture of composite materials in general and some examples of fatigue crack deflection in composite structures are described.

1. INTRODUCTION

Flaws in composite materials often deviate significantly from their nominal direction of growth which is on the Mode I crack plane normal to the stress axis under uniaxial far-field tensile loading. Such marked deflections in crack profile are developed when the crack tip encounters *local* discontinuities such as the interface between two materials or phases in laminated and coarse duplex structures, the grain boundaries in the matrix or the interfaces between the matrix and the uniformly or randomly-dispersed particles, whiskers or short fibers. The phenomenon of crack deflection (e.g., references [1] and [2]) is promoted by various mechanisms including (i) delamination at interfaces, (ii) embrittling effects of certain environmental species, (iii) *local* stress state, (iv) abrupt load excursions and (v) certain transgranular failure processes such as crystallographic crack advance in metals. As a deflected (or branched) crack has a lower effective crack tip driving force compared to a straight (or linear) crack subjected to the same nominal far-field stresses, the phenomenon of crack deflection is often considered a means for improving the fracture behavior in materials where deflections in crack profile can be intentionally induced (e.g., [3]). In fact, linear elastic fracture mechanics have been reported for predicting improvements in toughness achieved through crack deflection processes in ceramic composites containing different shapes, sizes and distributions of secondary particles [3] and in monolithic metallic materials artificially aged to produce microstructures of widely varying extent of slip planarity (e.g., [4]).

In cyclic loading, the phenomenon of crack deflection influences propagation rates by inducing mixed-mode displacements *locally* at the crack tip as well as by enhancing the so-called "crack-closure" level during unloading from the peak stress of the fatigue cycle [1,2]. Deflections in crack path are strongly dictated by the orientation and directional properties of the materials constituting a composite structure and can occur in random orientations in three dimensions. In view of the extreme complexity of this problem and the paucity of a clear understanding of the mechanisms and driving force for mixed-mode deflected crack advance during fatigue, attempts to develop sophisticated three-dimensional models are at present unwarranted. Valuable quantitative insights and a parametric description of the trends in deflected crack growth behavior, however, can be gained by examining certain simplified cases of nonlinear crack advance.

With this objective, the intent of this article is to review some recent advances [1,2] in the modeling of *apparent* changes in propagation rates arising from uniform and periodic deflections in the path of a fatigue crack. A simple linear elastic model [1,2] is described, focusing only on the *consequences* of periodic tilts in crack profile in composite materials containing only *dilute* concentrations of deflection-inducing whiskers or particulates. The analyses provide a quantitative feel for the variations in cyclic crack growth rates as a function of the angle of deflection, length of deflection and the amount of net lateral displacement (mismatch) between the mating crack faces developed while unloading from the peak stress of the fatigue cycle. The usefulness of such calculations are discussed in light of the quantitative understanding of the trends in *local* mixed-mode fracture in composite materials in general and with particular reference to deflected fatigue crack advance in two specific materials: (i) a metallic composite containing a ferritic-martensitic dual phase microstructure and (ii) a powder metallurgy 2124 aluminum alloy with randomly dispersed SiC whiskers.

2. MODELING OF CRACK DEFLECTION

A discussion is presented here of the geometric models based on simple linear elastic analyses of crack deflection, recently proposed by Suresh [1,2]. Consider a segment of a nonlinear crack, of idealized geometry as shown in Figure 1(a), with periodic tilting deflections of orientations $+\theta$ and $-\theta$ degrees (about the Mode I crack plane) over a distance D and linear (undeflected) crack growth over a distance S . The length of each segment is assumed to be much smaller than the total length of this two-dimensional model crack in composites containing *small* amounts of deflection-inducing secondary phases. The *cause* of deflection is not the primary focus here; only the consequences of deflection due to periodic tilts are evaluated. Growth along S is purely in Mode I (tensile opening) so that

$$\Delta k = \Delta K_I \tag{1}$$

where Δk is the *effective* stress intensity amplitude and ΔK_I the *nominal* stress intensity amplitude derived from far-field loads. Growth along segment D , however, involves both tensile opening and sliding (Mode II) displacements. Such mixed-mode growth in the tilted region can be characterized* based on linear elastic solutions for kinked cracks (e.g., [5]) where the local Mode I and Mode II stress intensity factors, k_1 and k_2 , respectively, are given by

$$k_1 \approx \cos^3\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) K_I = a_{11} K_I \tag{2}$$

$$k_2 \approx \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \cos^2\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) K_I = a_{21} K_I \tag{3}$$

Fig. 1 (a) Schematic of a segment of an idealized tilted crack geometry.
 (b) Variation of $\Delta K_I/\Delta k_{eff}$ and $(da/dN)/(da/dN)_I$ with θ and D (ref. 1).

* When $D \leq 0.05 a$, $\frac{k_1}{K_I}$ and $\frac{k_2}{K_I}$ do not vary appreciably with D .

There are a number of fracture criteria, based on maximum principal stress [6], maximum strain energy release rate (G) [7], or minimum strain energy density factor [8], which provide an estimate of the effective driving force for mixed-mode crack advance. For *continued (co-planar or self-similar) growth* along the deflected span D, a reasonable assumption is [9,10]

$$G = G_I + G_{II} \quad (4)$$

This leads to an effective stress intensity, k, for growth along D

$$k = (k_1^2 + k_2^2)^{1/2} \quad (5)$$

Combining Eqs. (1-5), the weighted average of the effective stress intensity amplitude Δk_{eff} for each segment (of length D + S) for the deflected crack in Fig. 1 reduces to

$$\Delta k_{eff} = \left\{ \tilde{D} \cos^2 \left(\frac{\theta}{2} \right) + \tilde{S} \right\} \Delta K_I \quad (6)$$

where

$$\tilde{D} = \frac{D}{D+S} \quad (6a)$$

$$\tilde{S} = \frac{S}{D+S} = 1 - \tilde{D} \quad (6b)$$

In other words, to propagate a nonlinear crack at the *same rate* as a linear crack, it is required to provide an *apparently* larger nominal driving force, non-dimensionalized with respect to Δk_{eff} , given by

$$\frac{\Delta K_I}{\Delta k_{eff}} \approx \frac{1}{\tilde{D} \cos^2 \left(\frac{\theta}{2} \right) + \tilde{S}} \quad (7)$$

Note that Δk_{eff} is the effective driving force required to propagate a perfectly straight crack at an identical velocity. Furthermore, as the length of Mode I crack is measured along a direction normal to the loading axis, the propagation rate for a deflected crack, da/dN , is *apparently slower* than that for a linear crack, $(da/dN)_L$, subjected to identical values of effective driving force. Thus,

$$\frac{da}{dN} = (\tilde{D} \cos \theta + \tilde{S}) \left(\frac{da}{dN} \right)_L \quad (8)$$

Fig. 1b shows both the apparent increase in $\Delta K_I/\Delta k_{eff}$ and the apparent decrease in $(da/dN)/(da/dN)_L$ with increasing values of θ and D.

A perfectly elastic deflected fatigue crack closes only at zero or negative loads and there is no contact between the fracture surfaces at tensile loads. It is now known for both monolithic and composite materials, however, that during the unloading part of the fatigue cycle, a net lateral mismatch can develop between the fracture surfaces for a linear-elastic crack (e.g., [1,2]). It leads to a mechanical contact of fracture surface asperities before the minimum load of the fatigue cycle is reached. This phenomenon, termed crack closure [11], promotes a further reduction in the effective stress intensity amplitude for deflected cracks where rough fracture surfaces are generated due to nonlinear crack growth. The amount of mismatch is a function of the extent of crack-tip plasticity, environmental effects and local deformation behavior involving slip characteristics and is known to be of the order of 10 to 50 percent of the cyclic Mode I opening displacement in monolithic metallic materials [2].

Figure 2 schematically shows the opening of a deflected fatigue crack at the peak of the loading cycle for purely Mode I far-field stresses. As the crack is unloaded it is assumed that a net lateral displacement (mismatch), x_2 , is developed when the two surfaces first come into contact after a Mode I unloading displacement $x_1 = x_2/\chi$. Based on the derivation in Figure 2, it can be seen that this effect results in premature asperity contact and can be expressed in terms of a non-dimensional closure stress intensity amplitude

$$\frac{\Delta K_{cl}}{\Delta K_I} \approx \left[\frac{\chi \tan \theta}{1 + \chi \tan \theta} \right]^{1/2} \quad (9)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \Delta \delta^* &= \Delta \delta - x_1 = x_2 \tan \theta \\ \chi &= \frac{x_2}{x_1} \end{aligned} \right\} \Rightarrow \frac{\Delta \delta^*}{\Delta \delta} = \frac{\chi \tan \theta}{1 + \chi \tan \theta}$$

$$\frac{\Delta K_{cl}}{\Delta K_I} = \left[\frac{\Delta \delta^*}{\Delta \delta} \right]^{1/2} = \left[\frac{\chi \tan \theta}{1 + \chi \tan \theta} \right]^{1/2}$$

Fig. 2 Schematic of the opening and closing of an idealized deflected crack and the derivation of closure stress intensity factor levels (ref. 2).

Note that closure is geometrically feasible only when the minimum crack opening displacement during the fatigue cycle is greater than the height of the asperity, $D \sin \theta$. This phenomenon will lead to a further reduction in the effective driving force for a deflected crack so that

$$\Delta k_{eff} = (\Delta K_I - \Delta K_{cl}) [\tilde{D} \cos^2(\frac{\theta}{2}) + \tilde{S}] \quad (10)$$

Thus, the ratio of the apparent to the nominal driving force under the combined influence of mixed-mode growth and fracture surface mismatch reduces to (Eqs. 8 and 9)

$$\frac{\Delta K_I}{\Delta k_{eff}} \approx \left[\frac{1}{\tilde{D} \cos^2(\frac{\theta}{2}) + \tilde{S}} \right] \left[1 - \left\{ \frac{\chi \tan \theta}{1 + \chi \tan \theta} \right\}^{1/2} \right]^{-1} \quad (11)$$

Figure 3 shows the dependence of $\Delta K_I/\Delta k_{eff}$ on θ for $\tilde{D} = 0.25$ and 0.75 and $X = 0.25, 0.50, 0.75$.

Fig. 3 Variation of $\Delta K_I/\Delta k_{eff}$ with θ for several values of \tilde{D} and X .

3. IMPLICATIONS FOR CRACK GROWTH RESISTANCE

In order to evaluate the implications of the changes in crack geometry to overall growth behavior, consider an arbitrary reference growth curve for a perfectly straight crack, denoted by the solid line in Figure 4a. The particular choice of this reference curve does not influence in any way the trends in fatigue behavior predicted by the model. The sole objective here is to address the following question. Given the fatigue crack growth data for a material containing a straight crack, how does its fatigue resistance vary as the crack is deflected through some structural modification in the material (i.e., when θ and \tilde{D} change from 0 to some positive value)? Figures 4a and 4b show such variations in fatigue crack growth rates with θ for the reference material and for \tilde{D} of 0.5 and 0.75, respectively. Here the apparent increase in stress intensity factor amplitude to propagate the deflected crack at the same rate as a linear crack (Eq. 7) and the apparent reduction in the measured growth rates of a deflected crack (at an equivalent effective driving force Δk_{eff} as a straight crack (Eq. 8)) are used to predict the deflected crack growth behavior. Figure 4c (derived from Eqs. 8 and 11) shows that a 25 percent mismatch ($X = 0.25$) can cause a substantial increase in fatigue crack growth.

Figure 4a

Figure 4b

Figure 4c

Fig. 4 Influence of θ (degrees) on fatigue crack growth behavior for zero mismatch and (a) $\tilde{D} = 0.5$ and (b) $\tilde{D} = 0.75$; (c) denotes effect of mismatch on fatigue crack growth behavior for $\theta = 45^\circ$ and $\tilde{D} = 0.75$.

The above results represent a simple attempt in quantifying the implications of crack deflections to fatigue failures where the crack profile can be altered through changes in the microstructure. These models reviewed here (following refs. [1] and [2]) pertain to *continued* deflected crack growth (occurring over several thousand fatigue cycles) along the kinked path, with the length of the tilted segment being substantially greater than the normal undulations (e.g., striations) typically observed in the fatigue fracture path. The predictions are clearly valid in situations where the extent of crack-tip plasticity is much smaller than the length of deflections developed over thousands of fatigue cycles and where tilting deflections dominate mixed-mode behavior. More rigorous analyses to extend this simplified model to the realistic three-dimensional situations are difficult at this time because of the limitations in the development of fracture mechanics solutions to complex crack geometries having tilts and twists. Simple calculations of effective stress intensities for some idealized geometries of tilted and twisted cracks [2,3,12] suggest that in the absence of any mismatch, the tilted and twisted geometry leads to a substantially larger reduction in effective k than the purely tilted geometry. As the extent of mismatch increases, however, simple two-dimensional analyses of tilted cracks lead to effective stress intensity factors comparable to those obtained for three-dimensional (tilted and twisted) shapes with similar extent of deflection [2].

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

4.1 Metallic Composites with Ferritic-Martensitic Duplex Structure

The material studied was a high purity Fe/2Si/0.1C steel with a composition (in weight pct) of 0.09 C, 2.01 Si, < 0.005 Mn, < 0.005 S, 0.005 P, < 0.005 Cr, 0.06 Ni, 0.03 Mo and < 0.01 V. The processing history of this plate material and detailed descriptions of heat treatment procedures and the resulting microstructural characteristics can be found in refs. [1] and [13]. Fig. 5 shows the heat treatment cycles and the optical micrographs for the intermediate and step quenching conditions. The intermediate-quenched (IQ) structure (iced-brine quenched from an austenitizing temperature of 1150°C, reheated intercritically for 40 minutes at 1020°C, and then requenched) displays a composite with a fine fibrous martensite (58 volume pct) within a ferrite matrix. The step-quenched (SQ) procedure (rapidly cooled to 910°C from the austenitizing temperature of 1150°C, held for 40 minutes and then iced-brine quenched) results in a composite microstructure with coarse martensite (32 volume pct) embedded in a continuous ferrite matrix. The room temperature mechanical properties for the two materials are summarized in Table I.

Fig. 5 Heat treatment cycles and resulting duplex microstructures in Fe/2Si/0.1C dual-phase steel following intermediate and step quenching.

The fatigue crack propagation rates for the two composite microstructures are plotted in Fig. 6 as a function of the nominal stress intensity factor range, ΔK_I , at a load ratio $R = 0.05$. The step-quenched composite structure has a markedly superior resistance to cyclic crack growth than does the intermediate-quenched material. The morphology of the fatigue crack at low growth rates is indicated in the optical micrographs of Fig. 7. The fine distribution of martensite in the ferrite matrix leads to a linear crack advance in the intermediate-quenched condition (Fig. 7a), whereas pronounced deflections in crack path occur at the ferrite-martensite interface when the ferrite matrix consists of "chunks" of martensite as in the step-quenched heat treatment

TABLE I
Properties for Fe/2Si/0.1C Dual-Phase Steel

Heat Treatment	Ferrite Particle Size (μm)	Volume Fraction Martensite (Pct)	Yield Strength (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	Redn. Area (Pct)
IQ	9	58	590	805	71
SQ	103	32	635	900	33

Prior austenite grain size is 237 μm for both IQ and SQ structures.
Connectivity of Martensite (Pct) is 84 and 64 for IQ and SQ, respectively.

Fig. 6 Fatigue crack propagation rates plotted against nominal as well as effective stress intensity factor range for IQ and SQ structures. The effective stress intensity factor range values were obtained from Eq. (12) after accounting for experimentally-measured closure.

Fig. 7 Examples of crack profiles in IQ (Fig. a) and SQ (Fig. b) microstructures at low stress intensity range levels.

(Fig. 7b). Such beneficial fatigue response of the SQ structure is observed even when the growth rates are replotted versus the effective stress intensity factor range accounting for experimentally-measured closure (Fig. 6). Here

$$\Delta K_{\text{eff}} = K_{\text{max}} - K_{\text{c}} \quad (12)$$

Figure 8 shows the predictions of the effect of crack deflections (using Equations [7] and [8] with IQ data as reference ($\theta = 0^\circ$ and $\bar{D} \approx 0$) and taking $\theta \approx 45^\circ-75^\circ$ and $\bar{D} \approx 0.25-0.50$ for the SQ condition. Such information, in conjunction with the observations of crack profiles (Figs. 7a and 7b), indicate that crack deflection processes account for a substantial proportion of the differences in the fatigue behavior of these two materials. The predictions of crack closure levels (Equation [11]) are not compared with experimental results because of the paucity of reliable information on the extent of mismatch (X) and its dependence on microstructure in these duplex steels; they are discussed in detail by Suresh [2] for other systems.

Fig. 8 Predictions of the effect of crack deflection with IQ data as reference with $\theta = 0^\circ$ and $\bar{D} = 0$, and taking $\theta = 45^\circ$ to 75° with $\bar{D} = 0.25$ to 0.50 for the SQ condition.

4.2 Aluminum-SiC Composite

The metal-matrix composite used in this study is a structure consisting of 13.2 volume pct SiC whiskers randomly dispersed in a PM 2124 aluminum matrix. The average diameter of the 2124 particle was about $50 \mu\text{m}$. The SiC whiskers had an average length of $40\text{-}60 \mu\text{m}$ and an average length to diameter ratio of 75. Both the unreinforced PM 2124 alloy and the material reinforced 13.2 volume pct (15 weight pct) with SiC whiskers were fatigue tested in the (T4) condition after similar processing and aging treatments. The room temperature mechanical properties of the two alloys have previously been measured [14] and can be summarized as follows: While the matrix material had a *minimum* yield strength, $\sigma_y \approx 300 \text{ MPa}$, ultimate strength, $\sigma_u \approx 450 \text{ MPa}$ and elongation, $e \approx 13\%$ (all of which strongly depend on the processing procedures), the reinforced structure had $\sigma_y \approx 450 \text{ MPa}$, $\sigma_u \approx 680 \text{ MPa}$, and $e \approx 4\%$. The elastic moduli of the unreinforced and reinforced materials were about 75 and 110 GPa, respectively. The heat treatment leading to the T4 condition comprised of solution-treatment at 766°K for one hour, water quench and room temperature aging for a minimum of 96 hours. Fatigue crack growth experiments were performed in the laboratory environment on 6.3 mm thick center-cracked specimens machined in the L-T orientation from 12.75 mm thick plates heat treated to the -T4 condition. Fatigue cracks were initiated under far-field cyclic compression following which cyclic crack growth data were obtained in tension (see ref. [15] for details). This section presents only the *preliminary* results of a large ongoing program dealing with the fatigue behavior of metal-matrix composites.

Figure 9 shows the variation of fatigue crack propagation rates with a nominal stress intensity factor range ΔK_I for the unreinforced and reinforced PM 2124 tested in the laboratory environment ($\sim 23^\circ\text{C}$ and 40% RH) at $R = 0.1$. Although considerable scatter exists in the measured values of da/dN , the Al-matrix composites exhibits a far superior resistance to fatigue crack advance at lower growth rates than the unreinforced PM 2124. This is evident from the higher threshold stress intensity range values. The data shown in Fig. 9 are also consistent with those obtained by other researchers in SiC reinforced 6061-T6, or other 2XXX series aluminum alloys (e.g., ref. [16]). The precise mechanistic details for this apparently beneficial crack growth behavior of SiC-reinforced Al have not been examined thoroughly; processes such as fiber pullout/breakage enhance fatigue failure at high ΔK levels (e.g., Fig. 10). Preliminary results obtained by a Lockheed research group [14] reveal that an important contribution to the higher fatigue threshold and lower near-threshold crack growth rates of the 2124-T4 with SiC (compared to PM 2124-T4) may simply stem from a more tortuous crack path induced by the presence of the fibers. A quantitative study of the extent of crack deflection and comparisons with the deflection model predictions are under way.

Fig. 9 Fatigue crack growth behavior of unreinforced and SiC reinforced PM 2124-T4 aluminum, ● (ref. 14), ▲, □ (this work).

Fig. 10 Fractograph showing fatigue fracture surface of PM 2124 + 13.2 V/o SiC $\Delta K = 10 \text{ MPa} \sqrt{\text{m}}$ and $R = 0.1$.

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The present review of analyses and experimental results on crack deflection highlight the significant effects of nonlinear crack path on the resistance to fatigue crack advance in composite structures. Recent studies by Suresh and Vasudevan [1,2,17] on the effect of aging treatment on crack growth behavior in several conventional and lithium-containing ingot cast (monolithic) aluminum alloys also reveal the strong beneficial influence of grain boundary-induced crack deflection on fatigue. Here the improvements in crack growth resistance due to variations in crack path were observed to be in reasonable agreement with the predictions of the deflection model detailed in Section 2. Experiments involving other composite structures also show that the idealized crack deflection profiles described in Fig. 1 provide a physically-realistic picture of the fracture process. Figure 11, for example, shows the deflected crack growth behavior

Fig. 11 Crack propagation in a composite material comprised of alternate layers of C and SiC. The plane of the notch is perpendicular to the layers (ref. 18).

$\theta \approx 60^\circ$, $\bar{D} \approx 0.9$) in a two-dimensional ceramic/ceramic fiber composite. This was made of woven bundles of carbon fibers in a SiC matrix and fractured under quasi-static loading [18]. In this example the plane of the notch was machined perpendicular to the layer and crossed cloth and matrix interlayers alternatively. The corresponding quasi-static fracture toughness values of this composite were found to be superior to those of the material where the layers were parallel to the notch. Although similar information for cyclic fracture still awaits careful experimental documentation in several composite materials, it is hoped that the present analyses provide helpful guidelines for the quantitative interpretations of crack deflection in composites and where improvements in resistance to fracture through structural modifications offer challenging prospects. Experimental studies of variations in deflected crack growth rates due to controlled changes in the structure of composite materials are currently in progress.

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